

Government Participation in Public-Private Partnership and Public Housing Projects Delivery in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

ALADEJEBI, Olutoye Ade¹ ALO, Dolapo Tolulope² and ALO, Ayopo Bamidele³

¹Department of Project Management Technology, The Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria; E-mail: ooladejebi@futa.edu.ng

²Department of Project Management Technology, The Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria; E-Mail: dolapolope@gmail.com

³Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute (NBRRI); E-Mail: ayopoalo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study assessed government participation in public private partnership and public housing projects delivery in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study identified factors responsible for PPP projects abandonment and assessed the effect of government participation in PPP on housing projects delivery. Survey research design was used to gather data from respondents through the use of a structured questionnaire. 86 copies of questionnaires were sent out while 80 copies were retrieved for the analysis making a response rate of 93%. Descriptive statistic and appropriate inferential statistics (frequency, tables, mean, standard deviation and Regression) were employed for the data analysis using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). The findings revealed that the major factors responsible for PPP abandonment are corruption and lack of cooperation of parties involved, with a mean value of (4.25). The general assessment of the government participation in PPP on housing projects reveals that the major benefit is that it encourages use of resources for improved service delivery at an affordable cost, with a mean value of (4.70). The R Square (0.074) tells us that 7.4 percent of the changes in factors that can be attributed to government participation. The ANOVA and Regression coefficient results show a p-value of (0.090) which is insignificant. The study therefore concluded that there is no significant relationship between government participation in PPP and ineffective delivery of public housing projects in Akure, Ondo State.

Key words: PPP, Stakeholders, Privatization, Abandonment, Infrastructure

1. INTRODUCTION

Public-Private Partnership is a name that is being applied to different types of contractual agreements between the government and the private sector for the purpose of infrastructural development and service provision within a geographical location [1]. However, one of the challenges facing PPP strategy is lack of continuity in governance, because when a particular government starts a project and there is change in government before the project is completed, there is possibility of low delivery of some projects while the new government focuses on its own goal and objectives. An example of such PPP project that was affected by change in governance according to Sotola and Ayodele [2] is the Olokola FTZ Gas project which was conceived as a PPP venture involving Ogun, Ondo and a consortium company in the oil and gas industry. Though this project is not officially closed, the commitment from political leadership has greatly reduced and has affected the delivery of the project due to the change in governance [2].

It also refers to a form of cooperation between public agencies and private parties to finance, design, build/construct, renovate, manage, operate or maintain an infrastructure or service utility which will involve a form of risk sharing [3]. The practice of PPP in Nigeria is thoroughly affected by varying degree of issues that have affected the success of the overall scheme. As a result, PPP in Nigeria is not so great though at the same time not entirely doomed. This is because while some of the PPP projects were successfully executed, some did not exceed conceptualization stage. PPP infrastructure projects implementation in Nigeria is characterized with controversies, failures, delays, litigations,

revocations among others [4]. Thus, this study zeroed on the prevailing issue of government participation and public private partnership projects delivery in Akure, Ondo State.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to assess government participation in public-private partnership on public housing projects delivery in Akure, Ondo state. While the specific objectives are to;

- i. identify factors responsible for PPP housing projects abandonment in the study area; and
- ii. assess the relationship between government participation in PPP and public housing projects delivery in the study area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Public Private Partnership

Egbewole [5] believed that the allocation of sizable and, at times significant, elements of risk to the private partner is essential in distinguishing the PPP from the more traditional public sector model of public service delivery. There are two basic forms of PPP: contractual and institutional. Although institutional PPP has been quite successful in some circumstances, particularly in countries with well-developed institutional and regulatory capacities, contractual PPP are significantly more common, especially in developing economies. While there is no universal consensus about the definition of public-private partnerships, the following elements typically characterize a PPP: The infrastructure or service is funded, in whole or in part, by the private partner. Risks are distributed between the public partner and private partner and are allocated to the party best positioned to manage each individual risk. PPP is a complex structure that may involve multiple parties and relatively high transaction costs. PPP is a procurement tool where the focus is payment for the successful delivery of services (the performance risk is transferred to the private partner).

Oyedele [6-7] identified the essential features of PPP as follows: the Legal Framework must be sound because of the different objectives of the parties and there must be efficient and effective costing. The costing must take into consideration all the risks involved, the source of finance must be assured, accessible and sustainable, both parties must have technical knowledge of the infrastructure being developed though it may be at different levels, it must be based on value for money (vfm), must be economical, efficient and effective.

2.1.2 Factors Responsible for PPP Projects Delivery

The preferred and prioritized projects embarked upon by government in recent times appear to be synonymous with chronic and consistent case of misplaced priority. In order to score cheap endorsement and perpetuate themselves in power, politicians in collaboration with top civil servants increase expenditure and investment in white elephant projects that have no direct bearing on the lives of the masses and in most cases results in abandoned projects. Also, projects that are better handled by the private sector due to the experience they have on the job are handled by government. To this end, government sometimes misallocates resources and thereby clogs the growth of national output [3].

Oyedele [6-7], identified the challenges of the Kuto-Bagana Bridge over the River Benue, which is a PPP venture between the federal government, Kogi and Nasarawa State governments. One of the states, Nasarawa paid its counterpart fund of N1billion to the development partner; however other parties could not meet up with their commitment. According to Oluwasanmi and Ogidi [3], The Victoria Island-Epe Express Road also failed because the concessioner Lekki Concession Company (LCC) failed to carry along other stakeholders. Without adequate consultation and approval, LCC wanted to construct three toll gates within a distance of less than 5 kilometres. Concerned Nigerians kicked against the idea and threatened legal actions. From the above examples, it is seen that government participation actively in PPP related activities is very key to success of projects delivery.

The need to determine the processes of project procurement under the PPP arrangement led to the study of the ICRC [8] which is the official document regulating the practice of PPP in Nigeria. The Act provides nine stages for packaging a PPP project. These include identification and prioritization of the project; obtaining clearance from the National Planning Commission (NPC); Submission of the spending plan to the Ministry of Finance (MoF) and Debt Management Office (DMO) for appraisal; review of the cost and contingent liabilities of the proposed project by the MDA; inclusion of the accepted spending plan in the budget; approval of the budget by the Legislature; permission to move spending between different budget heads; disbursement of funds to MDAs and preparation and auditing of annual accounts. After these are done contractual payments under PPP projects are consolidated into national account [8]. The acceptability of any PPP proposal by the MoF and DMO is dependent on the credibility of the private partner, ability of the project to attract long term development fund, government priority, expected cash flows from the project and availability of third-party support. The ICRC Act seems adequate enough to regulate the practice of PPP in Nigeria yet, it is not without flaws.

2.2 Theoretical Review of Literature

2.2.1 Public-Private Partnership and Game theory

Kargol, Aneta – Sokól, and Ewa [9], postulated Public-Private Partnership and Game theory. Game theory provides simple tools, which allow observing dependencies between entities activity. Its greatest worth is contribution to

explaining the mechanism of competition and cooperation. Most of the relationships between entities are neither strict conflicting nor strict cooperative. Using the terminology of the game theory, most of the social interactions are non zero-sum games, which means games between players whose interests aren't either totally opposite or fully coherent. In other words, between players exist rivalry that does not exclude possibility of co-operation.

Due to a lot of entities engaged in Public-Private Partnership, such as government (Federal, State or Local) authority or a government-owned enterprise, project sponsors, construction companies, providers of necessary equipment, plant operators, insurers, etc., there must be cooperation amongst them all for effectiveness. This co-operation in some cases could be examined as a game. The better understanding of Public-Private Partnership games can decrease costs and potential losses. For the purpose of this research, Game theory was adopted because it studies the interaction between the parties involved in PPP and suggests better ways of doing things. It also provides simple tools, which allow observing dependencies between entities activity which shows that PPP is seen as a co-operation rather than a competition.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Ke, Wang, Chan and Cheung [10], carried out a study on the Research Trend of Public Private Partnership in construction Journals. The study was carried out by analyzing a series of Public-Private Partnership publications. The research made use of 4,106 published papers in seven selected journals and the method of data analysis was correlation. The research concluded that Public-Private Partnership is becoming an increasingly important vehicle to deliver public infrastructure development and public service. Thus, the research recommends that a better understanding of the research trend in Public-Private Partnership will enable practitioners to appreciate the key issues in Public-Private Partnership development, hence, better able to drive Public-Private Partnership projects which are seen as global trend in delivering major infrastructure projects.

Dabak and Dantala [11], studied Public-Private Partnership: The Answer to Nigeria's Development Challenges. The research was carried out among selected Public-Private Partnership projects in Nigeria. The research concluded that the public sector can be able to realize its objective of infrastructure development and the private sector to make her profit through complimenting the government's effort with finance, maintenance and so on. The study recommends that Public-Private Partnership as a concept should be properly defined by government, tackling insecurity in the country will go a long way to improve infrastructural development, and there should be establishment of required regulatory framework for proper implementation of Public-Private Partnership projects.

Oyedele [6-7], studied Construction Project Financing for Sustainable Development of Nigerian Cities. The research was carried out in selected cities in Nigeria. The researcher administered 200 copies of questionnaire to workers in construction firms within the study area. Description and Inferential method of data analysis was used with the aid of SPSS, Microsoft Excel, and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The research concluded that There is no method of procurement that is not feasible but the situation, size, technicality and the people managing the procurement method. Corruption is the bane of our construction project procurement method. Public-Private Partnership projects have three constraints of quality, time and cost. In the face of corruption, any of these may be compromised. Partnering, a system of procurement that allows the participation of both parties in procurement is highly recommended for use in Nigeria construction project procurement, though it is not corruption-proof. Partnering is a win-win arrangement in which communication is open and all parties are risk takers.

Ogunsanmi [12], studied Critical Success Factors Determining the Implementation of Public-Private Partnership Projects. The research considered different critical success factors and it was carried out in Lagos State. Research questionnaire was designed to collect data from professionals. The study is a survey research and purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study from these respondents in PPP organizations that have been involved in PPP procurement. The research concluded that for successful implementation of PPP projects in Nigeria the contributive CSFs are: transparent and sound regulatory framework, comprehensive feasibility study, appropriate risk allocation, commitment, responsibility of public and private sectors, strong private consortium, government guarantee, realistic cost/benefit assessment, stable macro-economic conditions and sound economy policy that must be considered by both public agencies and private sector partners for future PPP projects in Nigeria and other developing countries. The study also recommended that public agencies should develop viable and robust legal and regulatory framework for PPP implementation as well as government undertaking sufficient public awareness campaign on need to pay for use of infrastructure projects on concession.

Elegbede, Olofa and Olojede [13], studied An Appraisal of the Performance of Private Developers in Housing Provision in Nigeria (Redan as a Case Study). The research employed the qualitative research approach and used descriptive and inferential statistics for the analysis of the data. The research concluded that except for the exemption to build low-cost housing, other incentives have not been well received by developers and are thus ineffective to promote the infrastructural system. The findings also implied that there is a need to reassess the existing incentives so as to increase the implementation of the housing delivery system in Nigeria. The study then went ahead to recommend that the proposed housing reform legislations must be passed without further delay to improving the investment climate and also in implementing international best practices which include sustainable approach of providing houses to the people by private developers (REDAN) in western Nigeria. There must be a macroeconomic stability, by keeping

inflation and interest rates down with a well regulated structure market that will give investors confidence about the economy, this will facilitate affordable housing supply by private developers (REDAN) to the expected housing needs.

Sanni [14], conducted a study on the Factors determining the success of public private partnership projects in Nigeria. A questionnaire survey was used as the main research instrument. The study concluded that the successful implementation of PPP projects is crucial to the development of social and economic infrastructures. The result of the factor analysis was able to identify the seven most important factors that are critical to a successful PPP project. These factors form the cardinal areas that governments should focus on for the improvement and development of the system to use PPP procurement method, especially in developing countries.

Enisan and Taiwo [15], studied Public-Private Partnership on Infrastructural Development in Lagos, Nigeria. The research however made use of questionnaires and interviews. The study concluded that the most significant potential benefits in Public Private Partnership in Lagos state include: revenue enhancement, cost savings and economic benefits, while the most significant potential risks in Public-Private Partnership include: limited competition, increased user costs or fees and political risks and further recommended that Public-Private Partnerships should be included in the curricula of higher institute of learning in order to enhance the level of knowledge of future professional about public-private partnerships. Government should also ensure that the public are well enlightened about public-private partnerships and they should make known the essential of public-private partnerships to the public and private sector so as to enhance private participation.

Adebayo and Anifowose [1], studied Institutional Arrangements and PPP Housing Project Outcomes: Case Study of Sunshine Garden Estate Oba-Ile, Nigeria. The research design employed for this work was the descriptive survey in which residents at SGE were randomly selected and the main research instrument used was a well-structured questionnaire. The research concluded that the PPP institutional arrangement in Ondo State is deficient; there is no enabling environment in the form of public consultation and the overall perception of the SGE residents has revealed that project monitoring was nonexistent with the private partners let alone to carry out construction unchecked and recommended that besides strengthening resources and regulations for the repression of corruption, preventive measures are important, for example, prohibiting intimate relations between staff members of the regulators' office and the private provider, implementing codes of conduct and training programs, and developing a strong corporate spirit supported by clear set of values for the public professionals.

Aliyu, Sani and Mohammed [16], conducted a study on Public Private Partnership in Nigeria and Improvement in Service Delivery: An appraisal. The study relied heavily on existing literature documents as its source of data. The study concluded that measures such as improved business environment, well-functioning regulatory framework and more efficient public sector will be crucial to the achievement of the gains of PPP and recommended that fiscal benefit in terms of tax holiday to infrastructure project and tax incentives to investors should be provided by government among many others.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Akure Metropolis, Ondo State, Nigeria. Ondo State is located in the South-Western part of Nigeria. The study was restricted to Akure South Local Government in Ondo State where the Ondo State Development and Investment Promotion Agency and the Ministry of Works, Land and Housing is located. Twenty (20) copies of questionnaire were sent to the Ondo State Development and Investment Promotion Agency and Sixty-six (66) copies were sent to the Ministry of Works, Land and Housing. The professionals with relevant PPP knowledge were purposively selected consisting of Project Managers, Civil Engineers/Builders, Architects and Quantity Surveyors making total of Eighty-six (86) copies of questionnaire being administered in the entire study area. Data collected in the course of this research was analysed with the use of descriptive statistics and inferential statistical tool such as regression analysis was used in testing the hypothesis through statistical packages for social science (SPSS).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Eighty-six (86) copies of questionnaire were distributed out of which eighty (80) which represents (93%) were returned. 60 respondents have between 0-10 years working experience and 20 respondents are between 11-20 years working experience. This implies that they must have had enough experience in handling PPP projects.

4.1 Investigating the Factors Responsible for PPP Housing Projects Abandonment in Ondo State

Table 4.1 assessed the factors responsible for PPP housing projects abandonment in Ondo state. Six factors were identified, which are: misallocation of resources, corruption, poor project conceptualization, inadequate funding, lack of cooperation of parties involved and lack of risk control mechanism. Corruption and lack of cooperation of parties involved jointly ranked 1st with mean of (4.25). Misallocation of resources ranked 2nd with mean (4.15). Inadequate funding ranked 3rd with mean of (4.13). Poor project conceptualization ranked 4th with mean of (3.85). Lack of risk control mechanism ranked 5th with mean of (3.65). The overall findings confirm that the major factors responsible for PPP abandonment of projects in Ondo state are corruption and lack of cooperation of parties involved.

This is in agreement with Punch Newspaper (October 25, 2017) which stated that the Bunu-led committee blamed mass failure of public projects over the years on corruption and also with Oyedele [6-7] who identified the challenges of the Kuto-Bagana Bridge over the River Benue, which is a PPP venture between the federal government, Kogi and Nasarawa State governments. One of the states, Nasarawa paid its counterpart fund of N1billion to the development partner; however other parties could not meet up with their commitment which depicts a lack of cooperation of the parties involved in the project. According to Oluwasanmi and Ogidi [3], the Victoria Island-Epe Express Road also failed because the concessioner Lekki Concession Company (LCC) failed to carry along other stakeholders.

Table -4.1 Factors Responsible for PPP Housing Projects Abandonment in Ondo state

Factors	Mean	SD	Rank
Corruption	4.25	1.000	1
Lack of cooperation of parties involved	4.25	0.834	1
Misallocation of resources	4.15	1.223	2
Inadequate funding	4.13	1.60	3
Poor project conceptualization	3.85	1.069	4
Lack of risk control mechanism	3.65	0.934	5

Source; Field Survey, (2021)

4.2. The Effect of Government Participation in PPP on Public Housing Projects Delivery

Table 4.2 assessed the effect of government participation in PPP and public housing projects delivery in Ondo state. The benefit with the 1st rank is that government participation encourages efficient use of resources for improved service delivery at an affordable cost, with mean (4.70). Mostly, investment projects are implemented in due terms and do not impose unforeseen public sectors extra expenditures ranked 2nd with mean of (4.43), Encourages the development of more housing infrastructure while helping the government focus on other aspects ranked 3rd with a mean value of (4.35), More innovation is possible on Public-Private Partnership projects because they are based on output specifications which maximize the use of private sector skills ranked 4th with (3.78) as the mean value and it promotes multiple stakeholders participation in the provision of critical infrastructure ranking 5th with mean (3.63). The general assessment of the government participation in PPP on housing projects reveals that the major benefit is that it encourages use of resources for improved service delivery at an affordable cost.

This response supports Klijn and Koppenjan [17] that stated that the global recognition accorded PPP as an alternative to government provider approach is based on the notion that it promotes multiple stakeholders' participation in the provision of critical infrastructure and encourages use of resources for improved service delivery at an affordable cost.

Table -4.2 Effect of Government Participation in PPP on Public Projects Delivery

Benefits	Mean	SD	Rank
Encourages efficient use of resources for improved service delivery at an affordable cost.	4.70	0.461	1
Mostly, investment projects are implemented in due terms and do not impose unforeseen public sectors extra expenditures.	4.43	1.107	2
Encourages the development of more housing infrastructure while helping the government focus on other aspects.	4.35	0.887	3
More innovation is possible on Public-Private Partnership projects because they are based on output specifications which maximize the use of private sector skills.	3.78	0.856	4
It promotes multiple stakeholders' participation in the provision of critical infrastructure	3.63	0.848	5

Source: Field Survey 2021

4.3. Hypothesis Testing

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Government participation in PPP and public housing projects delivery in Akure, Ondo State.

The Pearson correlation value 0.272 in the model summary shows a weak positive correlation between government's participation and the delivery of public housing projects, but this is not significant with a p-value of 0.090. The R Square 0.074 tells us that 7.4 percent of the changes in factors that can be attributed to government participation.

The ANOVA and Regression coefficient results both with a p-value of 0.090 also reports an insignificant effect of government participation on the delivery of housing projects in Ondo state. We therefore conclude that there is no significant relationship between Government participation in PPP and ineffective delivery of housing projects in Akure, Ondo State.

Table 4.4: Regression Analysis Results

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
	.272 ^a	0.074	0.049	0.64411	0.074	3.030	1	38	0.090
a. Predictors: (Constant), GVT impact									
ANOVA									
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.			
	Regression	1.257	1	1.257	3.030	.090 ^b			
	Residual	15.766	38	0.415					
	Total	17.023	39						
a. Dependent Variable: Factors									
b. Predictors: (Constant), GVT impact									
Coefficients									
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.			
		B	Std. Error	Beta					
	(Constant)	5.701	0.956		5.960	0.000			
	GVT impact	-0.399	0.229	-0.272	-1.741	0.090			
a. Dependent Variable: Factors									
Source: <i>Field Survey (2021)</i>									

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

This study revealed that government involvement in Public Private Partnerships is not the cause of ineffective projects delivery in the state. Corruption however, is a stain that needs to be thoroughly cleansed from the system in order to birth more building projects as a result of Public Private Partnerships and an overall progress of the state.

A sound financial package is very essential to establishing a project, hence it should be established before project commencement, and favourable government policies would encourage private investors who wish to go into partnership with the government in housing projects delivery.

Ultimately, it was established that government participation encourages efficient use of resources for improved service delivery at an affordable cost and this reinforces the fact that a Public Private Partnership is often time the solution to affordable housing. Hence, it should be giving due regard and all parties involved should contribute not only towards a successful conceptualization but also towards the actualization of the project.

5.2. Recommendations

The following was recommended based on the study;

- i. Proper evaluation of the financial package brought by private investors should be made to ensure that they are capable of funding the project till completion.
- ii. A sound partnership package should be clearly outlined listing all the obligations of each partner and an agreement to uphold it, and liable to sanctions in case any party defaults.
- iii. External law enforcers should be established to curb corrupt practices in Public Private Partnerships.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adebayo, A. & Anifowose, O. (2017). Institutional arrangements and ppp housing project outcomes: Case study of sunshine garden estate oba-ile, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, 7(10), 01–11.
- [2]. Sotola, O. & Ayodele, T. (2011). *Public-Private Partnerships in developing countries: A Systematic Literature review, IOB Study- Initiative for Public Policy Analysis; Public Private Partnership Will It Fix Infrastructure in Nigeria*, 378/2013.
- [3]. Oluwasanmi, O. & Ogidi, O. (2014). Public private partnership and Nigerian economic growth: Problems and prospects. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(11), 136-138

- [4]. Oyewobi, L.O., Ibrahim, A.D. & Ibrahim, Y.M. (2012). *Investigating Optimum Conditions for public-Private Partnership in Health, Education and Housing Sectors in Nigeria In: Laryea, S., Agyepong, S. A., Leiringer, R. and Hughes, W. (Ed.) West Africa Built Environment Research (WABER) Conference, Ghana, 24-26 July.*
- [5]. Egbewole, Q. A (2011). *Examining public private partnership in Nigeria: Potentials and challenges.* A long essay submitted to the Faculty of Law, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- [6]. Oyedele, L. (2013) Avoiding performance failure payment deductions in PFI/PPP projects: Model of critical success factors. *Journal of Performance of Constructed Facilities*, 27 (3) pp. 283-294. ISSN 0887-3828 Available from: <http://eprints.uwe.ac.uk/21611>
- [7]. Oyedele, O. A. (2013). *Construction Project Financing for Sustainable Development of Nigerian Cities.* Abuja.
- [8]. ICRC. (2012). Nigeria PPP Review. *Nigeria Infrastructure Advisory Facility*, 1(1).
- [9]. Kargol, Aneta-Sokol, & Ewa. (2006). Public private partnership and game theory. *Gazdálkodás*, 15(19).
- [10]. Ke, J., Wang, S., Chan, P. C., & Cheung, E. (2009). Research trend of public private partnership in construction journals. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 10(1076).
- [11]. Dabak, & Dantala, P. (2014). Public-private partnership: The answer to Nigeria's development challenges. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(22), 358-368.
- [12]. Ogunsanmi, O.E. (2013). Critical success factors determining the implementation of public-private partnership projects.
- [13]. Elegbede O.T, Olofa S.A, and olojede I.O (2015). An appraisal of the performance of private developers in housing provision in Nigeria (Redan as a Case Study). *Int'l Journal of Advances in Chemical Engg., & Biological Sciences (IJACEBS)* Vol. 2, Issue 1(2015) ISSN 2349-1507 EISSN 2349-1515.
- [14]. Sanni, A. O. (2016). Factors determining the success of public private partnership projects in Nigeria, *Construction Economics and Building*, 16(2), 42-55. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5130/AJCEB.v16i2.4828>.
- [15]. Enisan, A., & Taiwo, W. (2016). Public-Private Partnership: The answer to Nigeria's development challenges. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(22), 358-368.
- [16]. Aliyu Idris, Sani Mustapha Kura, Mohammed U. Bashir (2013). Public private partnership in Nigeria and improvement in service delivery: An appraisal. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)* Volume 10, Issue 3 (Mar. - Apr. 2013), PP 63-71 e-ISSN: 2279-0837, p-ISSN: 2279-0845.
- [17]. Klijn, E.H. & Koppenjan, J.M. (2000). "Public management and policy networks: foundation of a Network approach to governance". *Public Management*, 2(2), 135–158.